

Investigations on the Reactions of Oxomolybdenum(v) Ions in the Environment of diverse Anions and different Coordinating Ligands

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Reactions of oxoanion species of quinquevalent molybdenum with the ligands like 2-cyanopyridine (Cpy), 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole (Pybmz) and dicarboxylic acids like malonic acid (mal) and oxalic acid (ox) lead to the formation of stable new salt $\text{CpyH}[\text{MoOCl}_4]$ its nonelectrolytic derivatives $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_4\cdot\text{Cpy}_2]$, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2\cdot\text{Cpy}_2]$ and an acetylacetonato complex $\text{CpyH}[\text{MoOCl}_3\cdot\text{acac}]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Reaction in solid state yielded some mixed oxochlorooxalato molybdate(v) and oxochloromalonomolybdate(v) e.g. $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{ox})\text{Pybmz}]$, $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{mal})\text{Pybmz}]$, $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{mal})\text{L}]$ (where L = 2,2'-bipyridyl or 1,10-phenanthroline). The composition of these complexes have been established by analytical, magnetochemical and spectrochemical studies.

It has been reported earlier¹⁻⁴ that the stability of the oxomolybdenum species is dependent on acidity of the solution, participating ligand to form the complex and the anions present in the environment. Present work involves investigation on the use of ligands like 2-cyanopyridine (Cpy), 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole (pybmz) and dicarboxylic acids like malonic acid (mal) and oxalic acid (ox).

It is known that oxo-ions of quinquevalent molybdenum show close resemblance with iron in both low and high spin state in many complexes. But such similarities have not been noticed in the present circumstances. The protonation of 2-cyanopyridine in concentrated HCl leads to the formation of CpyH^+ cation, contrary to the corresponding 2,2'-bipyridyl (Bipy), 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-pyridylbenzimidazole, which get their both the tertiary nitrogens duly protonated. It is interesting to note here that all these four organic bases containing tertiary nitrogens are capable of stabilising the oxomolybdenyl cations. Both the dicarboxylic acids mentioned here stabilise the oxomolybdenum ions preferably by heating in solid state in an inert atmosphere.

The present work deals with the isolation and study of the new salt $\text{CpyH}[\text{MoOCl}_4]$, its non-electrolytic derivatives $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_4\cdot\text{Cpy}_2]$, $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2\cdot\text{Cpy}_2]$ and an acetylacetonato complex $\text{CpyH}[\text{MoOCl}_3\cdot\text{acac}]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. In solid state reaction some mixed oxochlorooxalatomolybdate(v) and oxochloromalonomolybdate(v), e.g. $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{ox})\text{Pybmz}]$, $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{mal})\text{Pybmz}]$, $[\text{MoOCl}(\text{mal})\text{L}]$ (where L = 2,2'-bipyridyl or 1,10-phenanthroline) have isolated in pure state.

Results and Discussion

Results of the elemental analysis are indicated in Table 1. It has been observed that oxidation

state of molybdenum in all the compounds are very much close to the theoretical value of 5.

The magnetic susceptibilities of the compounds were measured by the Gouy method. The values are in fair agreement with the d^1 -configuration of the quinquevalent molybdenum. The small value for $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\cdot\text{Cl}_4\cdot\text{Cpy}_2]$ and still smaller for the hydrolytic product $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\cdot\text{Cl}_2\cdot\text{Cpy}_2]$, may be due to the presence of oxobridges⁵ with the possible Mo-Mo interaction.

IR spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. A strong band is observed at $950-970\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ vibration⁶. The metal oxygen chain ($-\text{Mo}-\text{O}-\text{Mo}-\text{O}$) bending vibration may be located in the broad bands in the region $700-800\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In the compounds $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_4\cdot\text{Cpy}_2]$ and $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2\cdot\text{Cpy}_2]$, cyanopyridine is coordinated to the molybdenum probably through isonitrile type of linkage because in these compounds IR bands appeared at $600-800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{N}-\text{M}$ of the $-\text{C}=\text{N}\rightarrow\text{M}$ group). The strong bands at $1650-1655\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be due to the coordinated pyridine⁷. The strong band at 1550 cm^{-1} may be assigned due to $\text{C}=\text{O}$ of acetylacetonato. The broad band at 3200 cm^{-1} of acetylacetonato complex is due to the presence of lattice water in the molecule.

The electronic spectrum of $\text{CpyH}[\text{MoOCl}_4]$ in 12 M hydrochloric acid and of its acetylacetonato derivative $\text{CpyH}[\text{MoOCl}_3\cdot\text{acac}]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in acetonitrile medium were recorded. The reflectance spectra of the two binuclear complexes $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3\cdot\text{Cl}_4\cdot\text{Cpy}_2]$ and $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2\cdot\text{Cpy}_2]$ were taken in solid state, in paraffin base, due to their insolubility in common solvents. Since the spectrum of $[\text{MoOCl}_4]^-$ ion seems to be very similar to that of $[\text{MoOCl}_5]^{2-}$ ion, it may be suggested that in concentrated HCl medium the following equilibrium exists,

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)			μ_{eff} B. M. (Temp. K)	Oxidation state of metal	ΔM
			Mo	Cl	N			
1.	CpyH[MoOCl ₄]	Bright green	27.32 (26.74)	38.72 (39.55)	7.22 (7.78)	1.69 (299)	5.16	—
2.	Mo ₂ O ₃ Cl ₄ ·Cpy ₂	Deep violet	33.06 (32.54)	24.43 (24.06)	9.03 (9.49)	0.33 (295)	5.16	—
3.	Mo ₂ O ₄ Cl ₂ ·Cpy ₂	Orange yellow	36.20 (35.89)	12.66 (13.27)	9.98 (10.46)	Diamag.	5.09	—
4.	CpyH[MoOCl ₃ .acac]·2H ₂ O	Reddish pink	20.90 (20.96)	22.51 (23.22)	6.30 (6.10)	1.28 (301)	5.01	—
5.	[MoOCl(ox)(Pybmz)]	Reddish brown	22.38 (22.28)	8.20 (8.24)	9.92 (9.75)	1.34 (300)	5.01	3.01
	Same compound using second method		22.49	8.22	9.88	—	4.96	4.00
6.	[MoOCl(mal)(Pybmz)]	Brown	21.66 (21.58)	8.18 (7.98)	9.48 (9.45)	1.40 (300)	5.00	3.63
7.	[MoOCl(mal)(Bipy)]	Reddish brown	23.77 (23.66)	8.69 (8.75)	3.52 (3.45)	1.56 (300)	4.97	5.26
8.	[MoOCl(mal)(Phen)]	Reddish pink	22.39 (22.34)	8.28 (8.26)	6.62 (6.52)	1.42 (300)	4.97	5.23

The electronic spectral data of the salt CpyH[MoOCl₄] conforms to the presence of MoOCl₄²⁻ ion in solution logically from the fact that [MoOCl₄]⁻ will obviously form [MoOCl₅]²⁻ in strong HCl medium. The MoOCl₅²⁻ ion belongs to C_{4v} point group having tetragonal structure with a short Mo—O bond. The observed two crystal field transitions, i.e. ²B₂→²E (I) and ²B₂→²B₁ at 18 800 and 22 470 cm⁻¹ and the remaining four charge transfer transitions are in good agreement with the previous observations⁸. However, in the case of CpyH[MoOCl₃.acac]·2H₂O, spectral transitions are somewhat different, since the C_{4v} point group of MoOCl₅²⁻ ion is changed to C_s symmetry. The spectral characteristics of this salt has been assigned on the basis of previous observations⁹ of the salt PyH[MoOX₂.acac]. The first transition due to d_{x²-y²}→d_{xy}, d_{yz} appears at 14 100 cm⁻¹ and the second due to d_{x²-y²}→d_{xy} at 19 420 cm⁻¹. The third band at 23 360 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to π→d_{x²-y²} ligand-metal charge transfer transition, whereas the intra-ligand (β-diketone) transition π₃→π₄ appears at 27 630 cm⁻¹. The spectral assignment of two dimeric compounds have also been done according to previous works.

The uv and visible spectra of the oxalato and malonato complexes were recorded using dimethylsulphoxide as solvent. The complexes [MoOCl(ox)(Pybmz)] and [MoOCl(mal)(Pybmz)] give four transitions around 13 500, 19 500, 23 250 and 27 000 cm⁻¹, whereas for the other two complexes, i.e. for [MoOCl(mal)(Bipy)] and [MoOCl(mal)(Phen)], five transition appear around 14 000, 23 200, 26 300, 32 250 and 42 000 cm⁻¹. These may be assigned to the following transitions : ²B₂→²E (I), ²B₂→²B₁, L→Mo charge transfer, ²B₂→²B₂ (I) and ²B₂→²B₂ (II). In explaining the spectra of these non-electrolytic complexes electronic transitions were reconciled with standard assignments for identical compounds⁸.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Estimation of Mo, Cl and N, and determination of oxidation states of molybdenum were done by similar methods^{3,4} applied to previous compounds. Oxalate was estimated as usual by standard potassium permanganate solution after separating molybdenum¹.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on Hilger UVISPEK and Varian 634 spectrophotometers.

2-Cyanopyridinium oxotetrachloromolybdate(v), CpyH[MoOCl₄] : Molybdenum trioxide (1.0 g) was dissolved in hot concentrated HCl (10 ml) with stirring. Then hydriodic acid (1 ml) was added to it and the solution was gently boiled to drive off liberated iodine. To the concentrated small mass, minimum quantity of HCl was added when a bright green solution was obtained. 2-Cyanopyridine (1 ml) previously acidified with concentrated HCl, was added to it and the mixture stirred well. It was cooled in ice-cold water and saturated with hydrogen chloride gas, when a bright green crystalline solid was obtained. The product was dried under reduced pressure over solid KOH, (2.0 g).

Oxo-μ-oxodichloro(2-cyanopyridine)molybdenum(v), [Mo₂O₃Cl₄·Cpy₂] : 2-Cyanopyridinium oxotetrachloromolybdate(v) (1.0 g) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of absolute ethanol and the solution was heated to boiling. It was then cooled and to the cold solution ether was added stirring continuously when a deep-violet solid was obtained. It was dried under reduced pressure, (1.2 g).

Oxo-μ-dioxochloro(2-cyanopyridine)molybdenum(v), [Mo₂O₄Cl₂·Cpy₂] : A mixture of 2-cyanopyridinium oxotetrachloromolybdate(v) (1.0 g) and distilled water (5 ml) was heated to boiling with constant

stirring when an orange-yellow solid was obtained. It was dried under reduced pressure, (1.0 g).

2-Cyanopyridinium oxotrichloroacetylacetonatomolybdate(v), dihydrate, CpyH[MoOCl₃.acac.].2H₂O: CpyH[MoOCl₄] (1.0 g) was refluxed for 1 h with acetylacetone (10 ml). Initially the solution became green in colour but ultimately changed to dark-pink. The solution was then cooled to room temperature and absolute ethanol was added when a dark coloured pasty mass was obtained. On trituration with ethanol and ether, the mass gave a reddish-pink product which was under reduced pressure, (0.6 g).

Oxochlorooxalato-2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole molybdenum(v), [MoOCl(ox)Pybmz]: Freshly prepared PybmzH₂[MoOCl₅] (~1.0 g) was mixed thoroughly with solid powdered oxalic acid (0.3 g) in 1 : 1 mole ratio and the resulting mixture was heated at 135° in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide till the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceases. The reddish brown product obtained was washed with minimum quantity of dehydrated ethanol until free from unreacted oxalic acid and dried under reduced pressure over solid KOH, (0.6 g).

The same compound was also prepared by the reaction of oxotrichloro 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole molybdenum(v) (1.0 g) with oxalic acid (0.5 g) in 1 : 1 mole ratio to yield the oxochlorooxalato molybdenum(v) derivative (0.4 g).

Oxochloromalonato-2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole molybdenum(v), [MoOCl(mal)Pybmz]: This compound

was prepared following the same procedure as above using PybmzH₂[MoOCl₅] (1.0 g) and malonic acid (0.29 g) in 1 : 1 mole ratio to yield the brown product, (0.5 g).

Oxochloromalonato-2,2'-pyridyl/1,10-phenanthroline molybdenum(v), [MoOCl(mal)L] (where L=2,2'-bipyridyl or 1,10-phenanthroline): These compounds were prepared by heating the corresponding salts of molybdenum i.e. BipyH₂[MoOCl₅] and PhenH₂[MoOCl₅] with malonic acid (0.3 g) respectively, in solid state in an atmosphere of dry carbon dioxide at 150°. The colour of the products were reddish brown (0.60 g) and reddish pink (0.62 g) respectively. The analytical data of the compounds are given in Table 1.

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